

Examining the Impact of R&D Intensity on Near-Term Share Price Movement: A Comparative Analysis of the U.S. Technology and Industrial Sectors

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Abstract:

This paper examines how financial markets and participants price research and development (R&D) expenses in the short term, with a focus on U.S. technology and industrial firms. Though historically R&D has been known to drive long-term firm performance, in the short-term it is not clear to investors how R&D should impact valuation, as it can create uncertainty and potentially delayed returns. Using quarterly financials and stock price data, this study analyzes how changes in R&D intensity can impact stock price performance over intraday, interday, and quarterly time periods. Regressions were performed on the firm, sector, and pooled levels, with the S&P 500 used as a market control to isolate the causal effect at hand. Findings suggest that there is a negative relationship between R&D intensity and short-term share price movement. This effect was found to be the strongest and most significant in technology firms, with the intensity of the effect growing across longer time horizons. These results indicate that investors interpret R&D as a source of uncertainty in the short-term for technology firms.

Keywords: Research and Development(R&D); R&D Intensity; Stock Returns; Technology Firms; Industrial Firms; Market Reactions; Share Price Movement

Introduction:

R&D, also known as research and development, refers to expenses consisting of capital allocated to increasing organizational knowledge, developing new products or technology, or testing new designs. In the U.S., from 2020-2023, R&D expenditure rose from \$537 to \$721 billion at a CAGR of ~7.5%. The large amount of capital put towards R&D is largely concentrated in a few key industries.

The largest proportion of the \$691.5 billion in R&D performed by businesses with 10 or more domestic employees in 2022 was conducted by the manufacturing sector (54%) (Table DISC-3). Four-fifths of the \$691.5 billion was performed by five industries: information (including software publishing) at 26%; chemicals manufacturing (including pharmaceuticals and medicines) at 18%; computer and electronic products manufacturing (including semiconductors) at 15%; professional, scientific, and technical services at 11%; and transportation equipment manufacturing at 10%.

Even though R&D is a crucial part of the financial economy, investors don't respond to this expenditure in a clear pattern. According to the efficient market hypothesis, any changes or material news that affect the performance of companies are immediately reflected in their stock prices. However, factors such as the time period over which R&D is fully recognized in a company's valuation, as well as the limited nature of R&D disclosure, complicates this hypothesis in reality. Relative to R&D, capital expenditures are immediate, and lead to revenue-generated output, while the benefits of R&D are difficult to value in real time as returns can show up months or years later. This uncertainty raises the question of, "Do companies accurately price R&D expenditure in the short term?" These dynamics may also differ between industries. In technology companies, R&D is more integral to product innovation and competitive advantage than in industrial companies, where R&D is linked to operational and safety improvements.

This study aims to examine the relationship between R&D expenditure and near-term share price movement, with a focus on comparison between U.S. technology and industrial companies. By examining stock price data before and after earnings releases and controlling for S&P returns, this study isolates the effect of R&D expenditure on share-price movements. The null hypothesis of this study is that changes in R&D intensity have no significant effect on near-term share price movement. The alternative hypothesis is that changes in R&D intensity do have a significant effect on near-term share price movement, with this effect differing between the technology and industrial sectors.

This paper comes with three main limitations. First, there was a limited number of companies that were observed, as collecting data for these companies was time consuming, and many companies of interest did not explicitly report their R&D expenditure on their earnings. Second, there could be omitted variable bias, as other firm-specific factors could affect stock price changes. Finally, for the calculation of R&D as a % of revenue (measure of R&D intensity), a drop in revenue without subsequent R&D decreases could cause artificial inflation in R&D intensity, potentially biasing causality estimates.

Methods:

First, a batch of companies had to be selected for initial analysis. To source an initial list of companies, “publicly traded companies in the U.S. in <technology or industrial> industry” was searched, and companies were then filtered by industry applicability and market capitalization. “Industrials” and “technology” companies were broadly defined to include subsectors ranging from defense and manufacturing to consumer and enterprise software respectively. To confirm the companies were valid choices for analysis, 1-Month, 6-Month, 1-Year, and 5-Year stock price charts were cross-referenced to eliminate any companies with extremely cheap stocks (<\$10.00/share), or wildly volatile trading patterns (NYSE: GME). Each company was tagged with their New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) or NASDAQ ticker symbol and industry code in the data table. Only companies with robust “investor relations” websites and quarterly earnings read-outs and published reports were selected for inclusion in this study. Roughly 6 years, or 24 quarters of data was collected from each viable company.

To begin the analysis, different financial variables and metrics were collected for each company in order to standardize and interpret the data across multiple firms and sectors. Below is an explanation of the variables included in this study, as well as a justification for their inclusion.

(1) *Revenue* was used as a proxy to indicate company size in order to standardize R&D benchmarks.

(2) *R&D Expenditure* was the primary independent variable of interest. It reflects a company’s current and future commitment to product innovation and development. By tracking the ratio of R&D Expenditure to Revenue, innovation intensity can be reflected in short-term valuation expectations.

(3) *Earnings Release Date* was used to find stock price data, acting as an anchor to find stock price valuation before and after new information regarding the companies’ expenditures were released to the public. By looking at stock prices before and after, we can find the impact of R&D Expenditure by controlling for the S&P.

(4) *Total Liabilities*, *Shareholders Equity*, and *Net Cash Flow* were gathered to control for confounding variables in the analysis that might cause omitted variable bias in the regression calculation.

Figure I: AI Prompt for Automated Data Collection of Quarterly Earnings Read-Outs

"Task:

I will provide you with the body text of XXX's quarterly financial reports. You already have everything you need to solve this. All of the data required is explicitly contained within the reports I provide — nowhere else. For each report, extract and output one single row of spreadsheet data with the following columns, in this descending order of date:

- Year
- Quarter
- R&D Expenditure (for that quarter, in \$000,000s, as reported)
- Revenue (for that quarter, in \$000,000s, as reported)
- Total Liabilities (as of that quarter-end, in \$000,000s, as reported)
- Shareholders Equity (as of that quarter-end, in \$000,000s, as reported)
- Net Cash Flow (for that quarter, in \$000,000s, as reported)
- Earnings Release Date (the date the earnings press release was published, in MM/DD/YYYY format — not the SEC filing date)

Critical Rules (Non-Negotiable):

- Only extract information directly stated in the provided financial reports.
- Do not estimate, infer, assume, or hallucinate any values.
- Use only the exact sources I give you. Never pull data from anywhere else.
- If a value is not explicitly and clearly labeled in the provided data, leave the cell blank. Do not improvise.
- The "Earnings Release Date" must be the press release publication date, not the SEC filing date.

Output must be a no-code data table directly in the chat. No code blocks, no CSV/Excel/PDF attachments, no Markdown formatting. The format must allow me to copy-paste straight into Google Sheets or Excel with no formatting issues.

Final Output Requirements:

- Output only the requested columns in the exact specified order.
- Each report = one row.
- Present the data table directly in the chat, aligned by tabs or spaces, so it pastes cleanly into Google Sheets.

Example Output Format (in-chat table, copy-paste ready): Year Quarter R&D Expenditure Revenue Total Liabilities Shareholders Equity Net Cash Flow Earnings Release Date: 2025 Q1 \$X,XXX \$XX,XXX \$XX,XXX \$X,XXX \$X,XXX 04/24/2025"

To collect data for each company, large language models (LLMs) were utilized to extract the financial data from uploaded documents. The process for each company was to first go to their investor relations page and download quarterly and annual earnings releases. Then, those

documents were uploaded to the language models using the prompt displayed in *Figure I*. Earning releases were blocked in groups of four to avoid overwhelming or confusing LLM models. A large variety of LLMs were experimented with to determine which models would yield best experimental accuracy. Tested models include ChatGPT (4o, o3, 5, 5-Thinking), Claude (Sonnet 4.5, Opus 4.1), Grok (4, 4-DeepSearch), and Perplexity (via. GPT-5). Ultimately, ChatGPT 4o and 5 were used for the majority of data collection, other than earnings releases that had incomprehensible formats, which were recorded manually on the data table. To populate the data table, the outputted information from the LLMs was copy-pasted in descending order of fiscal *Year* and *Quarter*, and organized by *Company*.

To get stock-specific data, [NASDAQ.com](https://www.nasdaq.com) was used to download historical stock prices for each ticker, contained in the “Historical Quotes” tab. Downloading the “Max” amount of data gave 10 years of information, dated from the present. These files were then uploaded into the google sheet, each as a separate tab. A formula was then created within the data table to link the different tabs using VLOOKUP based on *Ticker* and *Earnings Release Date*. For each earnings release date and the next trading day (represented by *Next Trading Day*), both market open and close price data was collected for each ticker. Open price was represented as the price of the stock upon market exchange open (9:30 AM EST), and close price was represented as the price of the stock upon market exchange close (4:00 PM EST). A master sheet of S&P control prices was also collected using an identical methodology; individual S&P prices were anchored by *Earnings Release Date* to provide a standardized baseline for individual stock price movements. *Intraday Stock Price Change* was represented as the change in stock price from open on day $t=0$ to close on day $t=0$. *Interday Stock Price Change* was represented as the change in stock price from open on day $t=0$ to close on day $t=1$. An identical procedure was applied to calculate intraday and interday stock prices changes for the S&P.

Finally, to finish the data collection step, the entirety of the data table was reviewed to ensure there were no anomalies or irregularities (e.g. misattributed formulas or overlapping difference calculations between firms). The data was exported as a CSV file and then imported into R for initial analysis.

Analysis & Findings:

In R, the following analyses were performed on the data collected during the procedure. First, new column variables were calculated to begin analyzing the data, including:

- a. *rd_intensity_pct*: the percent of revenue spent on R&D
- b. *rd_intensity_change_pp*: change in R&D Expenditure as a percentage of revenue by quarter
- c. Intraday and interday return percentages were calculated for both individual stocks and the S&P control
- d. *leverage_ratio*: The ratio of *Total Liabilities* to *Shareholders Equity*
- e. *cashflow_margin_pct*: percentage of revenue that produces *Net Cash Flow* for the business
- f. Next quarter revenue (*revenue_next_dollars*) and revenue growth percentage (*rev_growth_next_pct*) were also calculated for the analysis.
- g. *intraday_sp_ret_pct*, *interday_sp_ret_pct*, *quarterly_sp_ret_pct* were all calculated for each time period within the data for each firm.

To begin the analysis, summary statistics including mean, median, and standard deviation were calculated across both technology and industrial sectors for R&D expenditure as a fraction of revenue. Then, the mean interday, intraday, and quarterly stock price changes were calculated. These findings were reported in *Table II*.

In this case it was important to run regressions to reveal the causal effect of changes in R&D expenditure on stock price movements, controlling for changes in the S&P.

$$\text{Stock Return (\%)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\Delta \text{R\&D Intensity}) + \beta_2(\text{S\&P Return}) + \varepsilon$$

Regressions were run on an individual level, an industry level, and across industries to isolate changes in different groups. Regressions were run for interday, intraday, and quarterly stock price changes to get a better understanding of how R&D changes affect stock price over different time periods. The three types of regressions run are described below:

- a. Pooled Regression: One regression was run across all companies and quarters which shows the market wide effect of R&D expenditure on stock price changes (*Tables II-IV*).
- b. Sector Regression: Separate regressions were then run for each sector, showing sector-level differences in the effect of R&D expenditure on stock price changes (*Tables V-VII*).
- c. Firm Regressions: Singular regressions were run for each company which captures a company's specific relationship between R&D expenditure on stock price changes (*Tables VIII-X*).

Table I: Summary By Sector: R&D Change And Average Returns

Summary By Sector: R&D Change And Average Returns										
Sector	N	R&D			R&D		R&D Change SD (pp)	Intraday Return Mean (%)	Interday Return Mean (%)	Quarterly Return Mean (%)
		R&D Percent of Revenue Mean (%)	Percent of Revenue Median (%)	R&D Percent of Revenue SD (%)	R&D Change Mean (pp)	R&D Change Median (pp)				
Industrials	205	4.145	4.049	1.620	0.005	0.003	0.823	-0.029	-0.069	2.784
Technology	259	23.289	18.075	14.379	0.124	0.076	2.532	-0.048	0.491	5.077

To summarize, there were 205 observations of industrial firms and 259 observations of technology firms. In technology companies, on average 23% of revenue is spent on R&D vs 4.1% in industrial companies. There was also a larger spread in amounts of R&D expenditure in technology companies vs industrial companies, with the standard deviation for tech being 14.4 vs 1.6 for industrial companies. The mean R&D as a percent of revenue was higher than the median, meaning that there were more companies with R&D less than the mean, and a few outliers that were influential on the mean, pulling it up. This is reflected in the high standard deviation for technology companies. On average, stock prices for technology companies grew 5.1% quarterly over the observed period relative to 2.8% for industrial companies. After collecting these summary statistics, three sets of regression were performed on the data.

Table II: Intraday Return On R&D Change [Pooled Regression, (Adj R² = 0.17)]

Pooled Regression: Intraday Return On R&D Change With S&P Intraday Control				
Term	Estimate	Std. Error	t	p
Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	-0.1152	0.0636	-1.8110	0.0708
S&P Intraday Return (%)	1.3390	0.1421	9.4207	0.0000

In a pooled regression it was found that a 1% change in R&D expenditure results in intraday stock price going down -0.11%. This effect is significant at the 10% level but not the 5% level, as there is a p-value of 0.07. This regression controlled for the S&P, and there was a p-value of 0.00. For every 1% change in the S&P over the observed period, there was a 1.33% increase in the stock price of the companies that reported earnings on that day.

Table III: Interday Return On R&D Change [Pooled Regression, (Adj R² = 0.17)]

Pooled Regression: Interday Return On R&D Change With S&P Interday Control

Term	Estimate	Std. Error	t	p
Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	-0.4259	0.1606	-2.6517	0.0083
S&P Interday Return (%)	1.5665	0.2201	7.1163	0.0000

In another pooled regression it was found that a 1% change in R&D expenditure results in a 0.43% decrease in interday stock price. The p-value for this regression was 0.0083, showing a very significant impact. This regression shows that over an interday period R&D expenditure has a 4x greater impact on stock price than over an intraday period in both technology and industrial companies. The p-value for the interday regression was also higher, showing more significance on the interday regression.

Table IV: Quarterly Return On R&D Change [Pooled Regression, (Adj R² = 0.24)]

Pooled Regression: Quarterly Return On R&D Change With S&P Quarterly Control

Term	Estimate	Std. Error	t	p
Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	-0.9640	0.3807	-2.5324	0.0117
S&P Quarterly Return (%)	1.1802	0.1031	11.4477	0.0000

Finally, quarterly stock price change was regressed on R&D expenditure, revealing a 0.96% decrease in quarterly stock price associated with every additional 1% increase in R&D expenditure. The p-value for this regression was 0.018, which is more significant than the p-value for the interday regression, but not as significant as the p-value for the intraday regression. As the observed period of time increased, there was an increasingly negative effect on long-term stock price with increases in R&D expenditure as a proportion of revenue. On average the stocks we analyzed grew by more than 1% with 1% increases in S&P share values, meaning that we likely analyzed high growth, prominent, and highly-demanded companies.

Table V: Intraday Return On R&D Change With S&P Intraday Control [Sector Regression]

Sector Regressions: Intraday Return On R&D Change With S&P Intraday Control

Group	Term	Estimate	Std. Error	t	p
Industrials	Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	0.0060	0.2409	0.0250	0.9800
Industrials	S&P Intraday Return (%)	0.7144	0.2481	2.8796	0.0044
Technology	Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	-0.1187	0.0626	-1.8963	0.0590
Technology	S&P Intraday Return (%)	1.7002	0.1689	10.0682	0.0000

Technology: $R^2 = 0.2926$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.2870$

There were no significant results found over an intraday period for industrial companies, as the p-value was greater than the accepted value of 0.10, and the estimated effect was near zero. For technology companies, there is a -0.11% intraday change in the stock price for every 1% increase in R&D expenditure, with a p-value of 0.05. This -0.11% change in stock price was also found in the pooled regression over an intraday period. For every 1% increase in S&P price, technology companies went up 1.70% (p=0.00), showing that technology companies overwhelmingly dominate S&P returns and drive long term growth. Meanwhile, industrial companies only have a 0.71% (p=0.0044) increase per 1% increase in S&P price, and lag behind their technology-sector counterparts.

Table VI: Interday Return On R&D Change With S&P Interday Control [Sector Regression]

Sector Regressions: Interday Return On R&D Change With S&P Interday Control

Group	Term	Estimate	Std. Error	t	p
Industrials	Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	0.0374	0.2912	0.1284	0.8980
Industrials	S&P Interday Return (%)	1.0264	0.1706	6.0164	0.0000
Technology	Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	-0.4875	0.2101	-2.3203	0.0211
Technology	S&P Interday Return (%)	1.9980	0.3643	5.4843	0.0000

Industrials: $R^2 = 0.1520$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.1436$

Technology: $R^2 = 0.1176$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.1107$

In this regression over an interday period, there were again no significant results found for industrial companies, as the p-value was again greater than the accepted value of 0.10, and the estimated effect was near zero. For technology companies there was a p-value of 0.021 with an estimated effect of -0.48%. This effect from the interday regression was 4x greater than the

effect for the intraday regression. The effect previously discussed regarding technology companies driving S&P growth is seen here as well, as technology companies went up 1.99% (p=0.00), while industrial companies went up 1.02% (p=0.00) with each additional 1% increase in the S&P market capitalization.

Table VII: Quarterly Return On R&D Change With S&P Quarterly Control [Sector Regression]

Sector Regressions: Quarterly Return On R&D Change With S&P Quarterly Control					
Group	Term	Estimate	Std. Error	t	p
Industrials	Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	1.2643	0.9865	1.2816	0.2015
Industrials	S&P Quarterly Return (%)	1.0294	0.0955	10.7758	0.0000
Technology	Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	-1.1698	0.4701	-2.4884	0.0135
Technology	S&P Quarterly Return (%)	1.3451	0.1817	7.4037	0.0000

Industrials: $R^2 = 0.3844$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.3780$

Technology: $R^2 = 0.1975$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.1907$

Finally, for the quarterly regression, there was a more significant result for industrial companies, as the p-value was 0.20 with a 1.26% estimated effect. However, there was a 0.98% standard error, which makes it hard to draw a conclusive result, as the estimated effect can vary for the industrials segment. Meanwhile, for technology companies there was an estimated effect of -1.16% with a p-value of 0.013. These sector regressions showed the same patterns as the pooled regressions.]

Firm Effects With $p < 0.20$

Effect of R&D intensity change on returns with S&P control

For each time period, each company with a regression coefficient p-value less than 0.2 was plotted on the above graph, and colored by time period. The x axis represents the effect of the R&D intensity on share price movement over the applicable time period. More than 60% of the dots fall on the left side of the y-axis, showing a primarily negative effect of R&D intensity on share price movement over all time periods. Another observation is that when one significant data point was observed for a company, that same company had another data point over 50% of the time. These data points were also almost always on the same side of the y-axis, showing consistency in the results obtained over different time frames.

Discussion:

Compared to industrial companies, on average technology companies have a higher R&D expenditure as a percentage of revenue. One explanation for this could be that in technology companies, R&D is critical to developing new products and making advancements, whereas in industrial companies it is often used to increase efficiency within manufacturing processes, and make incremental improvements to existing products rather than invent entirely new product lines (Wikipedia). This can also be a result of the fact that technology companies are relatively asset-light compared to industrial companies, and because they spend less money on capital expenditures, this money can be instead put into R&D (BCG).

Looking at summary statistics, for each sector mean and median were relatively close to each other, showing that in the data collected there were not any significant outliers. Looking at standard deviation, it was much higher in technology companies than industrial companies, which could be a result of industrial companies being more established and around for long periods of time, while technology companies are newer and can grow rapidly. Additionally, there's a lot of heterogeneity in technology companies in terms of their age, subvertical, and demand for R&D that is not present in industrial companies.

It was also observed that over a quarterly period of time, technology companies grew almost 2 times faster than industrial companies. This is demonstrated by the fact that technology companies make up almost all of the S&P returns across the market in 2022-2025 (Investopedia). Technology companies are also able to scale their businesses exponentially more efficiently than industrial companies are able to because of differences in capital structures; industrial companies require large amounts of capital to expand their business through factory and equipment purchases, whereas technology companies can grow without requiring large amounts of physical infrastructure (Wall Street Times). Technology companies adopt and implement new innovations like artificial intelligence at a higher rate than industrial companies. IT and Software Services had an adoption rate of 90% compared to a 55% adoption rate for manufacturing companies (Kataria, Mehta, 2024).

In the pooled regression over an intraday time period a statistically significant decrease in stock price caused by R&D expenditure was found at the 10% level. This could be a result of information asymmetry between managers and investors, as when earnings are released investors aren't sure where R&D capital dollars are going. This uncertainty in where R&D expenditure is going makes it harder to intrinsic value these companies, leading to fluctuations in stock price. (Su et. al, 2009) This information asymmetry makes the stock seemingly more risky to invest in, leading to a decrease in purchase orders by retail investors (Hamin, Chowdury, 2019). Since there is a strong positive relationship between R&D expenditure and short-term price volatility, stock prices sometimes go up as well. This explains the significance at the 10% level, but not the

5% level. Additionally, it's continually observed that for every 1% gain in the S&P, the chosen basket of companies returns 1.33%, explained by technology companies growing at a faster rate over the observed period compared to the S&P.

Meanwhile, regressing R&D expenditure on *interday* stock price changes revealed a statistically significant decrease of 0.43% in interday stock price with 1% increases in R&D expenditure ($p = 0.0083$), which is a 4x stronger effect than observed on the intraday level. This stark difference can be attributed to the market observing earnings releases in a slow, predictable way, not instantaneously adjusting to new information (Fink, 2021). For the same reason, we see the p-value decrease by a factor of 10 relative to the first pooled regression, as over a longer period of time, the market has a chance to remove and correct variability introduced on the intraday level.

In the pooled regression over a quarterly time period a similar statistically significant decrease in stock price caused by R&D expenditure was found. There was a 0.96% decrease in quarterly stock price for every 1% increase in R&D expenditure ($p = 0.018$), which is 2x as large as the magnitude of change observed within an interday period, but stretched over an additional ~99 days. This can be explained through the diminishing returns model of information spread in the market. As discussed in Bucci. et. al, 2019, more than 50% of the impact of new market information is absorbed and reflected in stock prices within a few hours, but prices can take 50 or more days to fully adjust and absorb the other 50% of the impact. The slightly higher p-value in this regression can be due to more factors being introduced to the market over a significantly larger period of time, such as new revenue estimates or information being released.

Moving over to the sector-based regressions, over an intraday period there were no significant results for industrial companies compared to a very significant result of -0.11% for technology companies. The insignificance for industrial companies can be explained by the fewer amount of data points collected, as there were 259 data points for technology companies and 209 data points for industrial companies. Since $n = 10$ companies and $n = 11$ companies were used in the industrial and technology pools respectively, less data was available for long time-frame industrial activity, potentially leading to the insignificant result. There was a high variability in the type of industrial companies sampled during this research, as there is a stark difference between Cummins (which operates in the engines and diesel industry) and RTX (which provides military and commercial systems to the government), and without long time-series data for some of these companies, the minute effect on stock price was obscured. R&D in industrial companies is also more incremental and process oriented than technology companies, meaning there is less dramatic or "exciting" news to respond to in R&D readouts on earnings day, contributing to less of a dramatic effect on stock price. Industrial companies realize the benefits of R&D expenditure over a longer time period than technology companies because

of the varied, process-improvement oriented nature of the spending, and therefore a short-term effect would be extremely hard to detect.

These effects were still present at the interday time scale for industrial companies, as there were again no significant results on an interday time frame. Meanwhile, technology companies followed a much stronger trend than seen in the intraday pooled regression, as in the pooled regression there was a 0.42 decrease compared to a 0.48 decrease in the sector regression for technology companies. The p-value for technology companies also went up from the intraday regression, from 0.06 to 0.02, as the market has had more time to realize earnings over a longer period.

Finally, for the quarterly sector-based regression, there was a much more statistically significant result for industrial companies ($p=0.20$), though this was not significant enough to draw conclusions from. It was interesting to see that there was a 1.26% estimated effect, as this was the first observation of positive effects from R&D expenditure on stock price for industrial companies. The data for technology kept following the same trend, as the estimated effect of R&D on quarterly stock price movement was -1.16% ($p=0.013$).

Intraday:

BA	Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	-1.5429	0.6432	-2.3988	0.0242
BA	S&P Intraday Return (%)	0.6432	0.5139	1.2515	0.2223

Interday:

BA	Change In R&D Intensity (pp)	-1.8702	0.7400	-2.5273	0.0182
BA	S&P Interday Return (%)	0.3062	0.4886	0.6267	0.5366

Looking at the significant data points and significant company size, Boeing presents an interesting opportunity for a case study to better understand the effects described above. The Boeing Company is the world's largest aerospace company with a market cap of \$187.97 billion, and a prominent manufacturer of space, commercial jets, and security systems (boeing.com). Regressing intraday share price movement on R&D expenditures, there was a -1.54% change in share price ($p=0.024$) for every 1% increase in R&D reported for Boeing. A similar trend was observed over an interday period as there was -1.87% change in share price ($p=0.018$). A press release by Boeing in 2016 shows that they reclassified over \$847 million of R&D expenditure into non-cash after-tax charges, which breaks down to \$1.33 per share, or about 1% of share prices in 2016. This is an example of how R&D expenditure could be interpreted by investors as

an issue, because consistent increases can be interpreted as signals for program complexity or cost overruns. For Boeing and other industrial companies specifically, R&D expenditure is tied to safety improvements and certifications, re-designments costs, and re-engineering costs. There are many documented examples of this pattern within Boeing (and other industrials companies):

- 2009, Boeing 787 Dreamliner, \$2.5 billion was reclassified
- 2015-2016, KC-46 Pegasus Military Tanker, \$1.4 billion was reclassified
- 2023-2025, 777X, \$2.5 billion was incurred due to delays and certification setbacks.

These examples of reclassification of R&D expenditure in Boeing can explain the generally negative effects of R&D expenditure on stock price movement in industrial companies. Similar to Boeing, cost overruns and safety certifications can detract capital and focus from developing innovative products and instead redirect it to less productive spending categories.

References:

1. Bloecker, K. "The Effect of R&D Expenditures on Stock Market Returns for Danish Firms." *The Danish Centre for Studies in Research and Research Policy*, 17 Dec. 2003, www.researchgate.net/profile/Carter-Bloch/publication/229050796_The_Effect_of_RD_Expenditures_on_Stock_Market_Returns_for_Danish_Firms/links/0f317530b3693a6236000000/The-Effect-of-R-D-Expenditures-on-Stock-Market-Returns-for-Danish-Firms.pdf
2. Boeing. "Boeing Reports Third-Quarter Financial Results." *Boeing Media Room*, 21 Oct. 2009, boeing.mediaroom.com/2009-10-21-Boeing-Reports-Third-Quarter-Financial-Results.
3. Boeing. "Boeing to Recognize Cost Reclassification and Charges to Second Quarter Earnings." *Boeing Investor Relations*, 21 July 2016, investors.boeing.com/investors/news/press-release-details/2016/Boeing-to-Recognize-Cost-Reclassification-and-Charges-to-Second-Quarter-Earnings/default.aspx.
4. Boeing. "Boeing Reports Third Quarter Results." *Boeing Investor Relations*, 29 Oct. 2025, investors.boeing.com/investors/news/press-release-details/2025/Boeing-Reports-Third-Quarter-Results/default.aspx.
5. Boeing. "Company Overview." *Boeing*, www.boeing.com/company. Accessed 26 Feb. 2026.
6. Boston Consulting Group. "Business Model Innovation: Asset Light Is Right." *BCG*, 30 Sept. 2014, www.bcg.com/publications/2014/business-model-innovation-growth-asset-light-is-right.
7. CFM International. "Slow Decay of Impact in Equity Markets." *CFM Insight*, no. 247, 23 Dec. 2022, www.cfm.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/247-Slow-decay-of-impact-in-equity-markets.pdf.
8. Chan, Louis K. C., et al. "The Stock Market Valuation of Research and Development Expenditures." *NBER Working Paper*, no. 7223, National Bureau of Economic Research, July 1999, ssrn.com/abstract=227564.
9. Chan, Su Han, et al. "Corporate Research and Development Expenditures and Share Value." *Journal of Financial Economics*, vol. 26, no. 2, 1990, pp. 255-276, [doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(90\)90005-K](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(90)90005-K).

10. Chakravarty, Anindita, and Rajdeep Grewal. "The Stock Market in the Driver's Seat! Implications for R&D and Marketing." *Management Science*, vol. 57, no. 9, 2011, pp. 1594-1609, doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1110.1317.
11. Cro, Silvia, et al. "Stock Market Reaction to the Recurring Incidents at Boeing: An Event Study Analysis." *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 22 May 2025, doi.org/10.1002/ijfe.3180.
12. Currim, Imran S., et al. "Effect of Analysts' Earnings Pressure on Marketing Spending and Stock Market Performance." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, vol. 46, no. 3, 2018, pp. 439-463, doi.org/10.1007/s11747-017-0540-y.
13. Damodaran, Aswath. "Research and Development Expenses." *New York University Stern School of Business*, pages.stern.nyu.edu/~adamodar/pdfiles/papers/R_D.pdf. Accessed 26 Feb. 2026.
14. EconomyCharts (RobertBartus). "If You Net Out the Mag 7 from the S&P 500, the Rest of the Market Has Barely Moved." *Reddit*, 2025, www.reddit.com/r/EconomyCharts/comments/115gz41/if_you_net_out_the_mag_7_from_the_sp_500_the/.
15. Ehie, Ike C., and Kingsley Olibe. "The Effect of R&D Investment on Firm Value: An Examination of US Manufacturing and Service Industries." *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 128, no. 1, Nov. 2010, pp. 127-135, doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.06.005.
16. Freihat, Abdel Razaq Farah, and Raed Kanakriyah. "Impact of R&D Expenditure on Financial Performance: Jordanian Evidence." *European Journal of Business and Management*, vol. 9, no. 32, 2017, pp. 73-83.
17. Graham, John R., et al. "The Economic Implications of Corporate Financial Reporting." *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, vol. 40, no. 1-3, 2005, pp. 3-73, doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2005.01.002.
18. Ho, Yew Kee, et al. "The Effects of R&D and Advertising on Firm Value: An Examination of Manufacturing and Nonmanufacturing Firms." *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, vol. 52, no. 1, 2005, pp. 3-14, doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2004.839943.
19. "The Mag 7 in Charts: How Big Tech Dominates the Market." *Investopedia*, 17 Dec. 2025, www.investopedia.com/the-mag-7-in-charts-how-big-tech-dominates-the-market-11866473.

20. Kataria, Jatin, and Dhruv Mehta. "AI Across Industries: A Comparative Analysis of Adoption and Impact." *International Journal of Innovations & Research Analysis*, vol. 4, no. 4, 2024, pp. 213-222.
21. Lev, Baruch, and Theodore Sougiannis. "The Capitalization, Amortization, and Value-Relevance of R&D." *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, vol. 21, 1996, pp. 107-138, [doi.org/10.1016/0165-4101\(95\)00410-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-4101(95)00410-6).
22. Lev, Baruch, and S. Ramu Thiagarajan. "Fundamental Information Analysis." *Journal of Accounting Research*, vol. 31, no. 2, 1993, pp. 190-215, www.jstor.org/stable/2491270.
23. National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics. *Discovery: R&D Activity and Research Publications*. NSB-2025-7, U.S. National Science Foundation, 23 July 2025, nces.nsf.gov/pubs/nsb20257/u-s-business-r-d.
24. Peters, Bettina, et al. "Estimating Dynamic R&D Demand: An Analysis of Costs and Long-Run Benefits." *NBER Working Paper*, no. 19374, National Bureau of Economic Research, 2016, www.nber.org/system/files/working_papers/w19374/w19374.pdf.
25. Peterson, Robert A., and Jaeseok Jeong. "Exploring the Impact of Advertising and R&D Expenditures on Corporate Brand Value and Firm-Level Financial Performance." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, vol. 38, 2010, pp. 677-690, doi.org/10.1007/s11747-010-0188-3.
26. Prasanthi, K., and D. Sundari. "A Study on Research and Development as a Determinant Factor for Innovation in Small and Medium Enterprise's (SME's)." *IJABER*, vol. 14, no. 14, 2016, pp. 10253-10263.
27. "Why Tech Has Become a Giant in Wall Street." *Wall Street Times*, 15 Apr. 2025, wallstreettimes.com/why-tech-has-become-a-giant-in-wall-street/.
28. "Boeing KC-46 Pegasus." *Wikipedia*, Wikimedia Foundation. Accessed 26 Feb. 2026, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boeing_KC-46_Pegasus.
29. "Research and Development Intensity." *Wikipedia*, Wikimedia Foundation. Accessed 26 Feb. 2026, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Research_and_development_intensity.
30. Xie, Heng, et al. "The Time-Lag Effect of R&D Investment on the Value of Listed Companies in China: A Cross-Industry Analysis." *Journal of Creating Value*, vol. 6, no. 2, 2020, pp. 1-15, doi.org/10.1177/2394964320923543.